

The Effect of Temperature, Noise and Lighting on the Work Productivity of PT. XYZ

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ABSTRACT:

The working environment at PT. XYZ on line 4 of the precast concrete manufacturing line has a high daily temperature and noise above the threshold, but the lighting is poor. Based on the observation of the work environment carried out on Line 4 of the production of precast concrete of PT. XYZ, there is temperature, noise, and lighting that still do not meet work standards. The main purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of temperature, noise, and lighting on worker productivity in the production process. This research was carried out observantly at PT. XYZ, West Java Province, Indonesia. The number of samples was 50 workers, and the sampling technique used was saturated sampling, i.e., all populations were sampled. The ambient temperature was measured using a thermometer, noise was measured using a sound level meter, lighting was measured with a lux meter, and work productivity was measured using a questionnaire. Data analysis uses multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the analysis showed that the temperature variable had a significant effect on the work productivity of workers ($p = 0.000$). The noise variable had a significant effect on the work productivity of workers ($p = 0.020$). Meanwhile, the lighting variable did not have a significant effect on work productivity ($p = 0.936$). However, simultaneously the variables of temperature, noise, and lighting affect work productivity significantly ($p = 0.000$). It was concluded that simultaneously the variables of temperature, noise, and lighting affected workers' work productivity.

Keywords: temperature, noise, lighting, work productivity.

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INTRODUCTION

The condition of the physical work environment that does not meet the standards will affect an employee who works on a production line. An employee who works certainly does not have a short

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time at the location, even has to work every day in the same place and for a long period of time. The high and low productivity of the workforce is influenced by work morale, safety, comfort, and the work environment. To produce quality products, production activities must be carried out effectively and efficiently so that productivity can increase. With this circumstance, the physical work environment must be considered in order to be able to work optimally [1-3].

Temperature, noise, and lighting are work environment factors that can affect work productivity [4-6]. The ambient temperature is generally expressed by the wet bulb temperature (WBGT) and the temperature in the workplace refers to the Ministry of Agriculture No. Kep 51/MEN/1999 with a working time of 75% and a break 25% at a moderate workload has a threshold of 28 °C [7-8]. Meanwhile, the noise is measured with a sound level meter with a threshold limit of 85 dB. Good lighting will also affect the production of workers.

Temperature, noise, and lighting will also affect the working capacity of employees in doing their jobs. An environment that is too hot will make you feel tired and sleepy, reduce stability, and make more mistakes at work [9-11]. Noise that exceeds the threshold will cause a person to be uncomfortable at work. Low lighting will also make a person unable to work properly and correctly and will even damage eye health. Poor temperature, noise, and lighting will be a bad working environment for workers. The impact of a poor work environment can result in decreased work productivity, work-related stress, work-related diseases, and can result in work accidents [12-14].

One of the subsidiaries of State-Owned Enterprises, namely PT. XYZ, was founded in 1997 with the aim of becoming a leading business in the Engineering Production and Installation (EPI) segment. PT. XYZ is engaged in construction. Currently, PT. XYZ has four concrete production lines, including in line 1 of pile concrete production, or better known by the community, namely earth nails. Line 2 produces electric pole-type concrete, then line 3 produces concrete for railway road bearings, and line 4 produces concrete such as corrugated concrete sheet piles (CCSP), linings, bridge bearings, piles, and railroad bearings.

The working environment at PT. XYZ on line 4 of the precast concrete manufacturing line has a high daily temperature and noise above the threshold, but the lighting is poor. The average temperature in the production process of line 4 is 35.2 °C. The process of stirring cement using a mixing machine has a high enough sound frequency so that the workers cannot hear clearly due to the noise arising from the mixing machine. The average noise in the production process of line 4 is 87.4 dB. The lighting available in the production process of line 4 is still minimal and relatively dark because the lighting is still substandard so that the workers cannot clearly see the objects around them while working. The average lighting in the production process of line 4 is 198.8 lux. These temperature, noise, and lighting conditions are classified as bad and can cause problems with occupational health. Poor environmental conditions will also lead to fragile productivity [13-16].

Based on observations of the work environment carried out on Line 4 of PT XYZ's precast concrete production, there are temperatures, noise and lighting that still do not meet work standards which causes worker performance to not be able to reach the specified targets. The main purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of temperature, noise, and lighting on worker performance in the production process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Object

This research was carried out observantly at PT. XYZ, West Java Province, Indonesia. The company produces various types of concrete, including piles, electric poles, railroad bearings, bridge bearings, CCSP, lining, and others. The object of study is the workers who are on line 4, which is the precast concrete-making line.

Population and Sample

The population of this study was carried out on workers who work in the production process of line 4 of PT. XYZ. The number of workers on line 4 is 50 workers, so the working population is 50. In this

study, a saturated sampling method was used [17], [18], where all populations were used as research samples, so that the number of samples used was 50 workers.

Research Instruments

The research instruments used in this study are:

- a. The temperature of the working environment is measured using a thermometer with degrees Celsius.
- b. Noise is measured using a sound level meter in dB.
- c. Lighting is measured using a lux meter with lux units.
- d. Work productivity is measured using validated questionnaires.

Research Flow

The flow of the research is as follows.

Figure 1. Research Flow

Data Analysis

The analysis method used in this study is by using a multiple regression analysis method with independent variables Temperature (X1), noise (X2) and lighting (X3), while the dependent variable is performance (Y). The conceptual model in this study is as follows:

Figure 2. Regression Model

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To perform multiple regression tests, classical assumption tests are carried out, namely data normality tests, heteroscedasticity, and multicollinearity tests. The data normality test used the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, obtaining a p-value of 0.05. This indicates that the distributed data is normal. Heteroskedasticity test This can be done by looking at the presence or absence of certain patterns on the scatterplot chart. In the scatterplot chart, it turns out that no specific pattern is found, so there is no problem with heteroskedasticity. As a way to strengthen the scatterplot test, there is another way, namely by testing the Park test, which is if the independent variable has a significance value exceeding 0.05. In the park test, a value of $p > 0.05$ was obtained so that it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the regression model of this study. Multicollinearity test by looking at the value Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If $VIF < 10$ or a value of tolerance > 0.10 , then there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the linear regression model. In this study, the VIF value was obtained for the temperature variable 1.287, the noise variable 1.252, and the lighting variable 1.066. This shows that there is no problem with multicollinearity. Based on the results of this calcic assumption analysis, it can be stated that the multiple linear regression analysis is eligible to be performed.

To see if there is a relationship between temperature, noise, and lighting variables on work productivity, the results of the multiple linear regression test are as follows.

Table 1. Multiple Linear Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-22.306	83.014		-0.269	0.789
	Temperature	-0.891	0.218	-0.578	-4.091	0.000
	Noise	0.799	0.332	0.335	2.404	0.020
	Lighting	-0.031	0.380	-0.010	-0.081	0.936

Dependent Variable: Work Productivity

Based on Table 1, the temperature variable obtained a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), which shows that the temperature variable has a significant effect on the work productivity of workers. In the noise variable, a significance value of 0.020 ($p < 0.05$) was obtained, which shows that the noise variable has a significant effect on the work productivity of workers. Meanwhile, in the lighting variable, a significance value of 0.936 ($p > 0.05$) was obtained, which shows that the lighting variable does not have a significant effect on the work productivity of workers.

The output results of the simultaneous F test are as follows.

Table 2. F-Test Output (Simultaneous)

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
1	Regression	17.269	3	5.756	6.151	0.001
	Residual	43.051	46	0.936		
	Total	60.320	49			
a. Dependent Variable: Work Productivity						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Temperature, Noise, Lighting						

Based on table 2 above, a significant value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$) was obtained, meaning that the variables Temperature, Noise, and Lighting together had a significant effect on the work productivity of PT XYZ workers in the production process of line 4.

Based on tables 1 and 2, a model of the equation of temperature, noise, and lighting variables on worker work productivity can be made as follows:

$$\text{Work Productivity (Y)} = -22,306 - 0.891 (X1) + 0,799 (X2) - 0,031 (X3)$$

Based on the regression equation, it can be explained that the constant value of -22.306 can be interpreted if the temperature, noise, and lighting variables are considered constant or do not change; then the performance of workers at PT. XYZ will remain at -22.306.

The results of this study are relevant to research conducted by other researchers who stated that working temperature affects worker work productivity [19-21].

Work in areas with a hot environment will cause an employee to feel thirsty easily because the fluids in the body are easily reduced, which will increase the risk of dehydration for employees [15,22,23]. So that employees will drink more often, this condition will cut the employee's working time. One of the impacts arising from poor work environment conditions is fatigue. Employees will feel tired quickly in poor working conditions so that employees' movements become slower and less enthusiastic in doing work. The impact that occurs due to a poor temperature work environment is that productivity is not optimal, so there is no increase in productivity carried out by employees in the production area. This is very detrimental to the company, where every company will definitely continue to strive to increase productivity in order to compete and survive in the business it is running.

According to Mehta et al [24], their research revealed that the level of background noise that is prevalent in crowded coffee shops or the sound of television playing in the living room is around 70 decibels; it was found that it can increase creativity when compared to a relatively quiet atmosphere of 50 decibels. This shows that an increase in noise levels can increase a person's creativity. In other sources, noise can have a positive effect on performance because it can increase alertness, attention, and activeness.

The lack of lighting support in a space will result in activities in the room being disrupted, for example, when too much lighting will result in impaired vision [25,26]. Lighting that is too high can have health and safety impacts such as glare, headaches, and stress. Lighting that is too high can interfere with a person's ability to complete tasks safely. This is because the eyes become tired or sore, which can lead to work errors.

Based on this discussion, it can be stated that temperature can partially affect work productivity significantly. Noise also affects work productivity significantly. Meanwhile, lighting does not have a significant effect on work productivity. However, simultaneously the variables of temperature, noise, and lighting have a significant effect on the work productivity of workers. These results can be a reference or basis for related parties to improve the work environment that still does not meet good work environment standards. Because with a comfortable work environment, workers can work more optimally so that the company's targets can be achieved. Therefore, it is recommended to PT. XYZ and other industry parties to make improvements to components that affect work productivity, such as temperature, noise, and lighting.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn: (a) Environmental temperature has a significant effect on the work productivity of PT. XYZ, (b) Noise has a significant effect on the work productivity of PT. XYZ, (c) Lighting does not have a significant effect on the work productivity of PT. XYZ, (d) Simultaneously, the variables Temperature, Noise, and Lighting have a significant effect on the work productivity of PT. XYZ. It is recommended to PT. XYZ and other industry parties to make improvements to components that affect work productivity, such as temperature, noise, and lighting.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in the research and creation of this article.

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